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Using Digital Science’s Dimensions database to track research with the UN Sustainable Development Goals

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Introduction

The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide a framework to achieve sustainable development globally. Given that universities have a critical role in helping the world achieve the SDGs through their research, the ability to acknowledge and strengthen academic contributions to the SDGs is paramount.

Digital Science has invested in providing a lens in Dimensions through which research can be viewed by SDGs. Understanding the Goals, how much current research interest relates to them, how collaborative they are, and how they relate to traditional research fields is a key part of what research managers, policy makers and strategists should be engaging within the next few years (Wastl et al., 2020). Dimensions has the ability to map and visualise research over time and across countries, in relation to SDGs.

The SDGs pose an interesting problem for automated classification as they are broad and varied in their definition, with relevant works not necessarily mentioning the specific terminologies that typically help to define traditional research classifications (Wastl, et al., 2021). Using Dimensions, Digital Science created a model from the complete set of 17 SDGs. The first version of the classification system was implemented in 2019 (Wastl et al., 2019). It has since been improved on and updated, and Version Two is set to be released in Dimensions imminently.

Using Dimensions’ SDG Classification to garner important insights on the societal impact of research globally

Combining SDG research classification and Dimensions' GBQ data platform

Digital Science has partnered with Google Cloud to remove barriers to data access, analysis and visualisation for organisations across the research and innovation ecosystem. With its new integration, the Dimensions database is now available to be analysed on BigQuery (GBQ), Google Cloud's serverless, highly scalable and secure multi-cloud data warehouse.

This partnership allows Dimensions to be used in large-scale analyses (Hook, & Porter, 2021). One example of this is the use of the GBQ data platform being applied in the context of the SDG classifier to analyse the impact case studies submitted to the UK's Research Excellence Framework (REF2014) to produce insights beyond publications (Fane, et al., 2021). For this analysis we leveraged Dimensions data and enriched it with data from the case studies via GBQ looking at citation patterns in SDG versus non-SDG publications underpinning the REF case studies.

For the work we are currently undertaking, we use Dimensions' SDG classifier and the GBQ data platform to measure progress towards achieving the SDGs from an academic perspective. This section of the paper will focus on the ability of Dimensions to look globally, focusing on the Global North/Global South to ascertain differences in SDG research for SDG2 "Zero Hunger".

Geolocation analysis - Global South versus Global North

An interesting angle for analysis of SDG-related publications is based on one of the key aspects of the SDGs - location. A geographical analysis examines the levels of research activity in different regions with the aim of understanding the global locus of SDG research, and the collaborative landscape. We highlight in a report on the release of the first version of Dimensions SDG classifier (Wastl, et al., 2020), showing the contribution and share of individual countries which differ substantially. Specific patterns, e.g. a European focus on a science and technology angle of environmentally (climate change) and socially focused (health) SDGs emerged for country specific contributions to research in the context of sustainable development.

Moving in to our analyses, first we look at SDG research volume as a ratio of the overall number of publications - by countries grouped into two global regions (Global North and South) and rank them by percentage of publications contributing to the SDGs, over the total number of research outputs by country in the same timeframe (2012- 2021). Figure 1 lists the relative strength of research output by country based on numbers of publications by countries in the Global South for research related to sustainable development. It is interesting to see that 50% of the top 10 are countries attributed to the Global South.

Figure 1. Ranked list of Global North and Global South countries by share of SDG-related research based on the overall national output by each country.

To gain further insights we selected SDG2 “Zero Hunger” to investigate if further trends or insights on the distribution of publications could be revealed. SDG2 looks primarily at food security, nutrition and sustainable agriculture, and is applicable to all countries and pertinent to the Global South in particular.

Figure 2. Ranked list of Global North and Global South countries by share of SDG-related research based on contributions to SDG2 “Zero Hunger”. The percentage displays the number of SDG2 related publications over the overall national output by each country

Figure 2 helps us to shed light on differences in SDG-related research in the Global North and Global South. To illustrate this we spotlight SDG2 to show that the extent of published research relating to this SDG is greater in the Global South with the top 29 countries producing research in this area being in this region. Based on the global average (see dotted line in Figure 2) there appear to be no countries in the Global North that have produced research related to SDG2 above this average.

Following the outcomes of our investigation thus far, we set out to compare the publication profile of two countries, one in each global region, to see if any further insights might emerge. We examine the collaboration profile based on a co-authorship analysis visualised by the VOSviewer (van Eck & Waltman 2010) in Dimensions (see Figure 3). What emerges is Zimbabwe, ranked top by share of SDG2 output, shows a varied and broad collaboration profile, particularly amongst other African nations in the Global South. The co-authorship analysis also reveals evidence of collaboration with countries in the Global North including the UK, the Netherlands, and Australia.

Figure 3. Collaboration and co-authorship analysis for SDG2 related publications from Zimbabwe

Another investigative angle taken was to look at concepts and themes which emerge within SDG2 related research in Zimbabwe (Figure 4A). We were interested in probing deeper into the research output for this country to see what areas within SDG2 related research have been undertaken. To do this we took a proxy measure for areas of research - the journals in which the research has been published - from which we could explore themes and concepts that emerge. The VOS viewer network analysis outlines in Figure 4A the journal titles and clusters

them in a way that reveals areas of focus. Journal clusterings that are environmental, agricultural and ecosystem related are revealed.

Figure 4. Comparison of journal titles in which Zimbabwe (4A) and Germany (4B) published research related to SDG2 “Zero Hunger”

4A Zimbabwe

4B Germany

Figure 4B highlights networks of closely related journal titles based on Germany's research contributing to SDG2. This comparison between Germany and Zimbabwe helps us understand any commonalities or differences. What we see is that Germany's SDG2 publication focus features in predominantly medical and health related journals whilst Zimbabwe's publication focus features in journals relating to the ecosystem, the environment and agriculture. Thus we can conclude that differences are greater than commonalities.

Conclusion

This paper provides a brief overview of the implementation of the UN SDG classification system developed in Dimensions and outlines how we are now able to combine innovative research classifications (SDG) with technology (GBQ), for large scale data analysis to gain new and deeper insights. One example we provide is using Google BigQuery and Dimensions together to analyse country level data and SDG related research to explore geographical differences and commonalities. We highlight this capability with an exploration of the research output in the Global South and the Global North in the context of SDG2 "Zero Hunger". Our findings in this ongoing work reveal the possibilities at our disposal for analysing SDG-related research in Dimensions at a greater level of granularity with the introduction of, and in combination with, GBQ.

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